

D3.5

CATALOGUE OF SERVICES TARGETED FOR THE PRIVATE SECTOR

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Deliverable abstract

A dedicated catalogue of services is developed in the frame of ENVRI-FAIR to address ENVRI private sector clients/users by defining and implementing strategies for strengthening RI innovation-cooperation awareness and preparedness and promoting industry uptake of ENVRI services in compliance with FAIR standards. The data collection for the catalogue is based on a survey aiming at analysing the current state of the relation between ENVRI and private sector and draw recommendations for strengthening this cooperation.

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D3.5 Catalogue of services targeted for the private sector

1 Introduction

ENVRI-FAIR (ENVironmental Research Infrastructures building Fair services Accessible for society, Innovation and Research) promotes the development of a set of FAIR data services for each of the RI participating in the project, which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

In this context, targeted collaborative actions are foreseen with the private sector to enhance the uptake of ENVRI data services. One of the goals of WP3 “Strategy for alignment with national and international stakeholders, community development and innovation activities” is to address ENVRI private sector clients/users by defining and implementing strategies for strengthening RI innovation-cooperation awareness and preparedness and promoting industry uptake of ENVRI services in compliance with FAIR standards.

In particular Task 3.4, which aims at spurring innovation by strengthening ENVRI innovation-related cooperation with industry in the development of key RI data service areas- products, technologies and training, is in charge of delivering a catalogue of services targeting use by private sector actors. This catalogue will improve the visibility of ENVRI to external users and stimulate the uptake of high quality, FAIR-compliant ENVRI services by industry clients/users. It will also be a valuable support for the development and implementation of strategies intended to strengthen innovation-competition awareness and preparedness in the RIs.

The work presented here is intended as a living document, which may be updated as new services become available during the ENVRI-FAIR project. It will also contribute towards the deliverable D3.1 A strategic action plan for enhancing uptake of ENVRI data by the private sector, due in M46 of the project.

The present catalogue is the result of a survey, designed to map out the landscape of ENVRI services used by private sector actors, and the main results of a dedicated innovation workshop organised at the end of 2021¹.

¹ [ENVRI-FAIR Innovation workshop report](#)

2 Objectives

Following the ENVRIplus “RI Innovation-Preparedness Roadmap”, published in 2019 in the framework of the ENVRIplus H2020 project², the present document intends to analyse the innovative products and services developed by ENVRI, and to spur them to better communicate those services towards industrial partners.

To this aim, the main content of this report is focused on the collection of the existing services targeted to the industry sector as well as on the main recommendations enabling better industrial use of the existing RIs services. Listing existing ENVRI services in a way users can locate, recognize, understand and access those to achieve their research goals will help users to better understand what RIs can provide to them. The main target of this report are industrial partners but could also be of use to public sector bodies interested in ENVRI services.

The catalogue could be further promoted in collaboration with ENVRI-FAIR WP2 communication team – for instance to be used at meetings where the ENVRI community has a booth - and the ENVRI-Hub developers.

3 Methodology

As a first step, ENVRI-FAIR WP3 team organised the first ENVRI-FAIR Innovation workshop on November 9th, 2021. This virtual workshop aimed at discussing how to better unlock and exploit the innovation potential of Research infrastructures and how to boost ENVRI cooperation with industry as providers of advanced services, procurers of leading-edge technologies and partners in the development of new data driven products and applications. Importance of having a clear landscape of the ENVRI and their services was stated by the private sector users. The catalogue of services is one way of raising awareness of ENVRI services. The main discussion points and conclusions of the workshop are reported in ENVRI-FAIR MS8. The outcome of the discussions will be fed into Section 6 of this report.

As a second step, Task 3.4 partners designed a survey targeting ENVRI managers to share the status of their RI collaboration with industry. The survey questions were designed by the WP3 team based on the workshop outcomes and previous surveys on innovation in RIs such as EMSO Innovations and Industry Service Group Survey on RI’s Facilities Current Relations with Industry. The table to collect descriptions of RI services is based on the methodology developed by the project CATRIS3 the Catalogue of Research Infrastructure services to have detailed descriptions of services available and be interoperable with the catalogue developed by CATRIS.

Based on previous work of WP3, it seems that the relationship of most ENVRI with industry is limited to interacting with suppliers on an ad hoc basis rather than cultivating companies as users or partners for innovation.

Industry can act as a supplier (of services, components, instrumentation), developing the “upstream” segment or as a user (of services and products developed by RIs) , developing the “downstream” segment. ENVRI are often in contact with industrial partners for the upstream activities, while activities in the downstream domain are rare. The survey was built to collect information on the facilitation and policy measures undertaken by ENVRI to cooperate with industrial partners, in particular for the downstream services, the description of services offered and the type and requirements of existing industrial users.

The questionnaire, which was created using Google Forms, was shared with the ENVRI-FAIR RI contact persons and the BEERI (Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures) members. To obtain a representative (at least 50%) pool of answers, reminders and targeted emails were sent directly to ENVRI DGs or managers. The deadline for replying was also pushed to mid-March 2022 (see Figure 1 below).

² ENVRIplus Deliverable [D18.5-RI-Innovation-Roadmap](#)

³ [CatRIS](#) is a H2020 project which offers an open portal to a harmonised and aggregated catalogue of services and resources provided by Research Infrastructures and Core Facilities across Europe. It is a bottom-up initiative, which is meant to be populated and run by RIs and CF service providers at European, national, regional and institutional levels. The search portal is also compatible with the EOSC catalogue.

Figure 1: Timeline of input collection for ENVRI Catalogue of Services targeted for the private sector

Only one answer per RI was expected. As most ENVRIs are distributed research infrastructures, some took some time to reply as they gathered inputs from their nodes. In total, 13 answers were collected from the 26 active RIs participating in the BEERI.

The management of the collected survey data followed the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) and no individual data was shared, only aggregated results. The individual answers and informed consent forms are stored at EMSO ERIC until the end of the project. All information and individual responses to the questionnaire will be kept confidential.

Additionally, respondents were asked to fill out and submit separate template tables with information about the services provided to industrial users. These descriptions are the basis for the catalogue of services, and can be found in section 5 of this document.

The survey was structured in 6 different sections:

- Introduction
- Respondent information: to gather information on RI and role of respondent
- Service definition: to indicate the field of activity of the RI
- Services offered by the RI: to define the services targeting industrial users, their scope and actions to strengthen cooperation with industry
- Usage of RI Services: collect data on implemented services to feed in the catalogue
- RI policies affecting the services offered

The questionnaire can be found in the Appendix of this document.

4 Results analysis

The current analysis is based on the results gathered by the survey submitted to the ENVRI.

The analysis aims at assessing the current situation in terms of available services and practises targeted to the private sector inside the ENVironmental Research Infrastructures, members of the BEERI. This phase represents an essential preparatory activity for the catalogue of services and provides the necessary information to integrate the different perceptions about the services and policies targeted towards the industry by the ENVRI Research Infrastructures. From the results, the status of the relationship with industry appears to be still in development. Depending on the maturity of the RIs the service provision is not yet fully centralised and the resources to promote and liaise with industry are scarce.

The results below are grouped in 4 main themes of the survey: landscape of the ENVRI respondents, ENVRI services description, industrial users profile, and finally measures targeting the private sector.

Landscape

Most ENVRI are organised as distributed research Infrastructures (12 out of 13 respondents). Distributed RIs enable the research community to use specific facilities, resources and services that are associated with different geographical locations. It is worth noting the diversity of structures: the number of nodes differ from one to another as well as the maturity of RIs. Some RIs are already established ERICs⁴ while others are in a project or preparatory phase. This structure impacts the way ENVRI operate and provide services as some are not at a stage where they can offer centralised, aggregated services to users.

The survey sample has been able to provide information regarding research infrastructures acting in all fields of activity of the Earth and environmental sciences (atmosphere, ecosystem/biodiversity, marine, solid earth); some of the RIs participating in the survey are dealing with more than one field of activity.

ENVRI Services

The survey respondents were then asked questions about services of their RIs to all user types. Figure 2 below illustrates the services offered by responding ENVRI in blue and the most requested services by industrial clients in orange. The results show that data services, analysis and applications are most frequently demanded by the industry. Remote or physical access to facilities are also requested, albeit less often.

⁴ ERIC stands for European Research Infrastructure Consortium (legal entity type)

Figure 2: Services offered by ENVRI and demand from industrial clients

ENVRI services are mostly used by users affiliated to academic or research organisations (see Figure 3). The private sector is only mentioned by 2 RIs. It is worth noting that in general RI data services are open to any interested users, typically under a CC-BY licence. There is often no direct means for the RI to know who the users are, except if specific user feedback processes have been established by the RI or if specific curation services have been requested.

Having access to more detailed information about how, for what purpose and by whom the services are used by the whole pool of RI users would be beneficial to better understand their requirements and expectations. Such data would have to be collected at individual RI level, and then summarised.

Figure 3: ENVRI services users' organisation type

Industry profile

The graphs reported below illustrate the RI’s answers on their industry clients. The origin of the collaborating companies is particularly important with regards to EU funding for transnational access. So far, national, local and international collaborations are well balanced as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: ENVRI services industry users’ size

Figure 5: ENVRI services industry users’ location

An open question about business areas of RIs customers was also asked to respondents but the results are very different from one RI to another. Several RIs mention “instrument manufacturers” but the other markets are very specific to the RI subdomain. The "instrumentation manufacturers" act as suppliers - making and selling instrumentation for RIs making observations - and are different from end-users. It may be worth repeating the exercise at this RI subdomain to get more precise information.

RI collaboration and measures targeting the private sector

Table 1: Existence of awareness raising measures towards industry at RI level

Measure	Yes	No	Other
Dedicated section of the RI website dedicated to industry or innovation	2	11	n/a
Regular strategy and/or Action Plan for collaboration with companies/industry	1	7	5
Existence of an Industry Advisory Committee (IAC)	3	10	n/a
Tailored services offered to private sector	1	11	n/a
Future plans to offer targeted services	5	7	n/a
Existence of physical / remote access policy	9	4	n/a
Existence of data policy	8	5	n/a
Specific policy/guideline for industry engagement	11	2	n/a
Hiring of an innovation officer	2	7	4

Table 1 depicts the specific measures undertaken by ENVRI respondents to promote industry / RI collaborations and invest resources in strengthening this relationship. Most respondents consider collaboration with industry to be important for their RI with an overall score of 4.1 out of 5. While the existence of data and access policies are rather developed in ENVRI, specific measures targeting industry are still under development or non-existent for most RIs. They are willing to engage more (via the organisation of specific events or via sharing success stories about their industrial relations).

Regarding Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and data ownership, for some RIs industrial users are treated the same way as other users, some don't have the case as they don't have industrial users yet, others have a specific clause for private sector notably with regards to the submission of data to the RI data centre (the submission is not mandatory when it could jeopardise a potential commercial use).

Regarding the development of an RI Catalogue of services, the figures presented in Figure 6 below are encouraging as more than 75 % of RIs recognize the importance of having a catalogue of services to help users obtain a clear understanding of the services offered.

Figure 6: ENVRI Development of service catalogue

The measures taken by the ENVRI to collaborate with the private sector are detailed in Figure 7. Respondents were asked the actual means of collaboration and the future actions to strengthen

collaboration. The importance of EU funded projects is a driver of collaboration as well as industry training programmes by RIs' central laboratories.

Figure 7: Measures to strengthen collaboration between RIs and industry

The awareness raising is expressed by respondents (see Figure 8) as the main barrier preventing the RIs collaborating with industry, followed by the need for dedicated funded projects enabling codesigned pilots with industrial partners, which was also largely selected by respondents.

Figure 8: Barriers preventing RIs from collaborating with private sector

5 ENVRI services targeting the private sector

The service description tables presented below were provided by 6 ENVRI. As mentioned earlier, most ENVRI don't have industrial users. Therefore the number of contributing ENVRI is less important than the number of respondents to the survey. It is worth noting that 5 out of the 6 respondents already have an RI catalogue of service or are implementing one. We intend to make this set of service descriptions, which together form the Catalogue of Industry Services, widely available to all interested parties.

Apart from the first version presented in this deliverable report, an online version is planned to be made available in the ENVRI-Hub in collaboration with ENVRI-FAIR developers and WP2 for further dissemination actions. This would not only be easier to update and maintain, but will offer users the possibility to sort and display the service information in different ways, for example according to service type, physical location, and cost model.

Table 2: Summary of the ENVRI services collected

	Name	Partner Organization
ACTRIS	Scientific exploration and enablement	Research services
	Innovative research	Innovation services
	Technological support and developments	Technical services
	Human resources development in atmospheric science and technology	Training services
	Data services	Research services, training services, innovation services, technical services, data services.
EMBRC	Access to marine biological resources and their ecosystems	Research and technical service
	Marine biological resources	Research service. Training on the cultivation, rearing, maintenance of marine organisms upon request.
	Facilities for experiments with micro & macro- marine organisms	Research and technical service. Training upon request.
	Technology platforms for marine biology	Research and technical service. Training upon request.
	e-services	Data service and research service. Training upon request.
	Accommodation and catering	Logistic service
EMSO	Virtual Access	Virtual access includes data portals, ERDDAP service, virtual research environment, and other data-related tools such as APIs, dashboards, and data products.
EPOS	EPISODES Platform (European Plate Induced Seismicity Observations & Datasets)	Data service, research service, technical service, innovation service, training service.
Eurofleets+	Transnational Access	Research Vessel and Large Exchangeable Equipment Access
	Education and Training program	Training.
ICOS	Observation data of carbon cycle.	Data.

5.1 ACTRIS services

	<p>ACTRIS - Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure</p> <p>ACTRIS is the pan-European research infrastructure producing high-quality data and information on short-lived atmospheric constituents and on the processes leading to the variability of these constituents in natural and controlled atmospheres. ACTRIS enables free-access to high-class long-term atmospheric data and offer access to our world-class facilities providing researches, from academia as well as from the private sector, with the best research environments and expertise promoting cutting-edge science and international collaborations. Customization of the services can also be provided by ACTRIS facilities to satisfy scientific and technical needs and meet the users' specific demands and interests.</p>
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Service Name	Scientific exploration and enablement
Location	Service available in all our partner countries. Actual sites and more info at this link .
Type of service	Research services
Service description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Physical access to instrumented observational and exploratory platforms for realisation of scientific experiments under ambient or controlled conditions; - Use of state-of-the-art instruments and equipment supporting scientific excellence.
Type of access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Physical ● Remote
Frequency of use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Depending on the selected facility
Price	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Free of charge (where possible) ● Possible fees based on the user and the demand
Availability period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Depending on the selected facility
Contact	SAMU at actris-head-office@helsinki.fi

Service Name	Innovative research
Location	Service available in all our partner countries. Actual sites and more info at this link .
Type of service	Innovation services
Service description	<p>Innovation services are dedicated to market-oriented applications and decision-making, targeting the use of ACTRIS facilities by the private sector. These services include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of new observation techniques for aerosol, clouds, and reactive trace gases. - Improvement of measurement and retrieval methodologies for aerosol, clouds, and reactive trace gases. - Exploration of instrument synergies and novel innovative research capabilities.
Type of access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Physical ● Remote ● Virtual
Frequency of use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Depending on the selected service
Price	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Free of charge (where possible) ● Possible fees based on the user and the demand
Availability period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Depending on the selected service
Contact	SAMU at actris-head-office@helsinki.fi

Service Name	Technological support and developments	
Location	Service available in all our partner countries. Actual sites and more info at this link .	
Type of service	Technical services	
Service description	<p>ACTRIS Topical Centres and National Facilities ensure up-to-date technology by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing measurement quality assurance and quality control procedures and tools; - Instrument-specific calibration, testing, and intercomparison; - Improving measurement and retrieval methodologies for aerosol, clouds, and reactive trace gases. 	
Type of access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Physical ● Remote 	
Frequency of use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Depending on the selected service 	
Price	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Free of charge (where possible) ● Possible fees based on the user and the demand 	
Availability period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Depending on the selected service 	
Contact	SAMU at actris-head-office@helsinki.fi	

Service Name	Human resources development in atmospheric science and technology	
Location	Service available in all our partner countries. Actual sites and more info at this link .	
Type of service	Training services	
Service description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training of users of ACTRIS data, products and tools and training of young scientists and users from new regions world-wide; - Best practice, knowledge sharing with and knowledge transfer to ACTRIS users. 	
Type of access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Physical ● Remote 	
Frequency of use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Depending on the selected service 	
Price	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Free of charge (where possible) ● Possible fees based on the user and the demand 	
Availability period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Depending on the selected service 	
Contact	SAMU at actris-head-office@helsinki.fi	

Service Name	Data services	
Location	Remote and virtual access provided by ACTRIS Data Centre (https://actris.nilu.no via https://www.actris.eu)	
Type of service	Research services, training services, innovation services, technical services, data services.	
Service description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to long-term, quality controlled ACTRIS measurements data from both observational and exploratory platforms, data products, and digital tools, through a single entry point, comprising raw data, automatic calibrated and quality-assured data - Meta data associated to the data products documenting data, data traceability and data flow, citation service, and data attribution, including version control - Data curation service for campaigns and dedicated research projects and initiatives, external or internal to ACTRIS. 	
Type of access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Remote ● Virtual 	
Frequency of use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Annual releases ● Near-real time data daily ● Depending on the selected service 	
Price	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Free of charge 	
Availability period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● N/A 	
Contact	SAMU at actris-head-office@helsinki.fi	

5.2 EMBRC services

<p>EMBRC EUROPEAN MARINE BIOLOGICAL RESOURCE CENTRE</p>	<p>EMBRC-European Marine Biological Resource Centre</p> <p>EMBRC supports all biological research of the marine environment, its biodiversity, and their interactions through access to marine biological resources and experimental systems.</p>
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Service Name	<p>Access to marine biological resources and their ecosystems</p> <p>EMBRC EUROPEAN MARINE BIOLOGICAL RESOURCE CENTRE</p>
Location	Service available in all our partner countries. Actual sites and more info at this link .
Type of service	Research and technical service
Service description	<p>Access marine ecosystems, including kelp forests, coral reefs, intertidal rocky shores, lagoons, mudflats, deep-sea environments as well as planktonic and pelagic communities.</p> <p>Special sites and extreme environments are also provided including: volcanic cold seeps, proxies for the future high CO₂/low pH oceans; polluted low-oxygen sites, for environmental impact studies, and artificial habitats such as renewable energy test sites for research on bio-fouling. Access to ecosystems is provided through the following platforms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coastal research vessels ● Scientific diving facilities ● Submersibles (ROV/AUV) ● In-situ sampling facilities and monitoring equipment ● Field stations <p>Specialised services are also available for tracking large marine organisms, such as mammals and turtles in their natural habitat, through satellite tag and sensor design. More info at https://embrc.eu/services/ecosystem-access.</p>
Type of access	on-site and remote
Frequency of use	> 5 times per year
Price	charged
Availability period	depending on the seasonality of the marine organisms
Contact	access@embrc.eu

Service Name	Marine biological resources
Location	Service available in all our partner countries. Actual sites and more info at this link .
Type of service	Research service. Training on the cultivation, rearing, maintenance of marine organisms upon request.
Service description	<p>The provision of marine biological resources for research purposes is at the core of the EMBRC services. Those include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biobanks • Culture collections • Marine model organisms • Rearing of aquaculture animals • Organisms collected in the wild • Taxonomic services <p>Organisms, cultures, strains, specific cell lines, tissues, tissue cultures and their DNA are available on-site or remotely; proper conditions are respected for shipment (e.g. use of dry ice). Taxonomic identification (classical and molecular) is offered through specialised services and professional taxonomists.</p> <p>EMBRC guarantees conformity with national and international regulations concerning collection, maintenance/cultivation and shipping of biological resources. Ethical standards and nature conservation requirements limit the availability and/or types of research on certain species such as mammals, turtles and those on the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Strict adherence to ethical standards and 3R policies (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle) is ensured. More info at https://embrc.eu/services/biological-resources.</p>
Type of access	on-site and remote
Frequency of use	> 5 times per year
Price	charged
Availability period	All the year round
Contact	access@embrc.eu

Service Name	Facilities for experiments with micro & macro- marine organisms
Location	Service available in all our partner countries. Actual sites and more info at this link
Type of service	Research and technical service. Training upon request
Service description	<p>Aquaria and culture facilities for both micro- and macro-organisms are the heart of EMBRC's marine research capacity. A wide range of facilities for maintenance, culture and experimental work on polar, cold, cool temperate, warm temperate and sub-tropical species is available. The facilities include in situ installations, mesocosms, bioreactors, and licensed tanks for holding marine vertebrates. Facilities are equipped for the manipulation of environmental conditions (e.g., temperature, pH, and light) and with water purification.</p> <p>The facilities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Aquaria and tanks ● Mesocosms ● Climate controlled rooms ● Wet laboratories ● Dry laboratories
Type of access	on-site and remote
Frequency of use	> 5 times per year
Price	charged
Availability period	All the year round
Contact	access@embrc.eu

Service Name	Technology platforms for marine biology
Location	Service available in all our partner countries. Actual sites and more info at this link
Type of service	Research and technical service. Training upon request
Service description	Latest technologies for fundamental & applied research in marine biology. EMBRC provides access to technological platforms to carry out initial analysis on their organisms when working at one of our sites. In particular, we provide access to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Standard molecular laboratories ● Bioassay platforms ● High-throughput molecular analysis tools ● Specialist equipment for structural and chemical analysis ● Scanning and transmission electron microscopy, confocal laser scanning microscopy, sample preparation ● Remote sensing and telemetry facilities include buoys, webcams, satellite tags of large marine organisms, and more
Type of access	on-site and remote
Frequency of use	> 5 times per year
Price	charged
Availability period	All the year round
Contact	access@embrc.eu

Service Name	e-services	
Location	Service available in all our partner countries. Actual sites and more info at this link	
Type of service	Data service and research service. Training upon request	
Service description	<p>Data handling tools & expertise</p> <p>EMBRC supports the development of coordinated data handling tools and expertise. EMBRC promotes e-infrastructure interoperability and standardisation in order to deal with large volumes of different types of data generated by marine research and to enhance collaboration between marine scientists, bioinformaticians and IT specialists. EMBRC provides services to process, curate, and store large datasets of sequences, metadata, historical time series and literature resources. In particular, we can provide access to datasets and data analysis tools and software</p>	
Type of access	on-site, virtual and remote	
Frequency of use	> 5 times per year	
Price	charged	
Availability period	All the year round	
Contact	access@embrc.eu	

Service Name	Accommodation and catering	
Location	Service available in all our partner countries. Actual sites and more info at this link	
Type of service	Logistic service	
Service description	Need a place to sleep while you conduct your research at one of EMBRC's partner sites? Many of our sites offer accommodation, as well as catering services.	
Type of access	on-site	
Frequency of use	> 5 times per year	
Price	charged	
Availability period	All the year round	
Contact	access@embrc.eu	

5.3 EMSO services

[EMSO – European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory](#)

EMSO is a large-scale European ESFRI RI for strategically placed, deep sea observatories with the essential scientific objective of real-time, long-term monitoring of environmental processes related to the EMSO – Observing the ocean to save the Earth. interaction between the geosphere, biosphere, and hydrosphere.

Service name	Virtual Access	
Location	Distributed infrastructures, including national data services, data centers at the regional facilities, and harmonised services through cloud resources from EGI.	
Type of service	Virtual access includes data portals, ERDDAP service, virtual research environment, and other data-related tools such as APIs, dashboards, and data products.	
Service description	<p>Key issues of virtual access are described as follows:</p> <p>(1) <i>Unified access to harmonised data</i>: Existing data aggregation systems provide ways for data harmonisation; however, this level of integration is not sufficient for developing those added-value services which constitute the novelty brought by EMSO inter- and multi-disciplinary nature. As a result, data services are designed to use and complement existing functionalities provided by these networks. An example of use of existing resources is the use of the NVS from BODC for curated vocabularies, which enhances interoperability within the domain.</p> <p>(2) <i>Interoperability and adoption of FAIR principles</i>: enhanced data discovery and search functionalities (adoption of curated vocabularies, refinement of the metadata catalogue), and interoperability of EMSO ERIC data through a federated ERDDAP system.</p> <p>(3) <i>Access to EMSO data</i>: application programming interfaces and data portal, which integrates identity management capabilities and features such as PID management.</p> <p>(4) <i>Data tools for delivering added-value (e.g., products, visualisation, analysis, etc.)</i>: multi-node added-value services, including EMSO customised data tools and the use of frameworks (e.g., virtual research environments and dashboards). These tools complement existing functionalities delivered by other systems.</p> <p>https://data.emso.eu</p>	
Type of access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> virtual (access to online resource) 	
Frequency of use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other: multiple times per day 	
Price	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Free of charge 	
Availability period	Available online at any time.	
Contact	Juanjo Dañobeitia. Juanjo.danobeitia@emso-eu.org	

5.4 EPOS services

	<p>EPOS - the European Plate Observing System</p> <p>EPOS, the European Plate Observing System, is a multidisciplinary, distributed research infrastructure that facilitates the integrated use of data, data products, and facilities from the solid Earth science community in Europe. With the goal of a better understanding of the active Earth system processes controlling earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, unrest episodes and tsunamis as well as those driving tectonics and Earth surface dynamics.</p>
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Service name	EPISODES Platform (European Plate Induced Seismicity Observations & Datasets)
Location	https://tcs.ah-epos.eu/
Type of service	Data service, research service, technical service, innovation service, training service
Service description	<p>The TCS (Thematic Core Service) for Anthropogenic Hazards (TCS-AH) provides facilities, time correlated datasets called episodes, and reference material on the EPISODES online platform to aid education and research on induced seismicity and hazards related to the exploration and exploitation of geo-resources.</p> <p>TCS-AH provides an innovative and accessible digital environment to enable e-research into anthropogenic hazards related to the exploration and exploitation of geo-resources via the EPISODES platform https://tcs.ah-epos.eu. The platform provides a comprehensive open data research infrastructure with services for data processing, analysis and visualization alongside grouped datasets, called "Episodes" and collaborative workspace features. Each episode provides time correlated industrial data (e.g. oil/gas production data, fluid injection rates, water reservoir levels) with geophysical data (e.g. induced/triggered seismicity, ground deformation) and associated geo- and metadata (e.g. bedrock geology, monitoring station positions) to facilitate episode and/or method-oriented research and studies into cause and effect.</p> <p>The innovation of TCS AH draws on the uniqueness of the integrated research infrastructures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Datasets - called "episodes" - that comprehensively describe a geophysical process that is induced or triggered by human activity, which under certain circumstances can become hazardous to people, infrastructure and the environment, • problem-oriented applications with the particular attention devoted to methods analysing connections between technology and geophysical response and resulted hazard, • flexible computational platform with an access to High Performance Computing resources, where a researcher can process the integrated data using the implemented applications. • virtual (access to online resource)

Type of access	
Frequency of use	Other: Every day basis
Price	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Free of charge
Availability period	n/a
Contact	Stanisław Lasocki , TCS AH Director, lasocki@igf.edu.pl Ania Leśnodorska, TCS AH ECO Manager alesnodorska@igf.edu.pl

5.5 Eurofleets+ Services

	<p><u>Eurofleets – An alliance of European marine research infrastructure to meet the evolving needs of the research and industrial communities</u></p> <p>The EUROFLEETS+ project will facilitate open free of charge access to an integrated and advanced research vessel fleet, designed to meet the evolving and challenging needs of the user community. European and international researchers from academia and industry will be able to apply for several access programmes, through a single-entry system.</p>
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Service Name	Transnational Access
Location	<u>Distributed RI, 27 Research Vessels, 5 AUVs and 7 ROV's</u>
Type of service	Research Vessel and Large Exchangeable Equipment Access
Service description	<p>Eurofleets+ provides access to 27 Research Vessels (RVs), five Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) and eight Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs). Key infrastructures have been selected based on their operational capabilities and their strategic geographic locations to meet the demands of the science community. The infrastructures are all highly capable and many are new, nearly new or recently refitted and equipped with the latest technologies. Smaller regional vessels are also available to facilitate training activities.</p> <p>Eurofleets+ provides geographic coverage to: the Mediterranean and Black Seas, Baltic and North Seas, North Atlantic (incl. Greenland and Norwegian seas) and Pacific Southern Ocean and Ross Sea.</p>
Type of access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● physical (hands-on access with users visiting the facilities in person) ● remote (users do not visit the facility in person)
Frequency of use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Depending on demand
Price	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Unit rate/Day ● Actual Costs
Availability period	N/A
Contact	<u>Eurofleetsplus@marine.ie</u>

Service Name	Education and Training program	
Location	Distributed Training Centres	
Type of service	Training	
Service description	The EurofleetsPlus Education and Training program offers training activities to early career technicians, marine scientists and (future) Research Infrastructure managers and will contribute towards EurofleetsPlus' objective of Building a Career in Blue Growth. Education, along with research and innovation, comprises the knowledge triangle and therefore plays a vital role in the advancement of knowledge, therefore, we aim to	
Type of access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● virtual (access to online resource) ● physical (hands-on access with users visiting the facilities in person) ● remote (users do not visit the facility in person) 	
Frequency of use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 3-5 times per year 	
Price	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Free of charge 	
Availability period	N/A	
Contact	Andrea Caburlotto OGS acaburlotto@inogs.it	

5.6 ICOS Services

	<p>ICOS - Integrated Carbon Observation System (icos-cp.eu)</p> <p>ICOS RI provides the long-term observations required to understand the present state and predict future behaviour of the global carbon cycle and greenhouse gas emissions. The objectives of ICOS RI are to provide effective access to a single and coherent data set to facilitate research into multi-scale analysis of greenhouse gas emissions, sinks and the processes that determine them, and to provide information, which is profound for research and understanding of regional budgets of greenhouse gas sources and sinks, their human and natural drivers, and the controlling mechanisms.</p>
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Service Name	Observation data of carbon cycle
Location	Online. Carbon portal in Lund, Sweden
Type of service	<p>ICOS Carbon Portal offers free access to high-quality and standardised greenhouse gas data, as well as to scientific and educational products and services. The Carbon Portal is a ‘one-stop shop’ for all ICOS data products.</p> <p>Carbon Portal manages data security, enforcement of the ICOS data policy, with user-friendly (and machine-friendly) internet- and other computer-network based interfaces. It organises long-term archiving of ICOS data products to guarantee their safe storage, future access and easy re-use.</p> <p>Data handling is the key for the high ICOS data quality. ICOS has created a transparent, documented and reproducible process throughout the data life cycle: from the measurements at the station via the Thematic Centres and the ICOS Carbon Portal to the user. All data distributed from the stations and going through the Central Facilities, are distributed in Carbon Portal. We are following the international developments in FAIR data management to build interoperable systems and make ICOS data free available in a transparent way.</p> <p>The Carbon Portal is hosted by the Lund University in Sweden and Wageningen University in the Netherlands.</p>
Service description	Data releases of measurements at our 150 stations.
Type of access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Virtual
Frequency of use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Annual releases ● Near-real time data daily
Price	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Free of charge
Availability period	n/a
Contact	Carbon portal director Alex.vermeulen@icos-ri.eu

6 How to develop further cooperation between industry and ENVRI

In the ENVRIplus Deliverable D18.5 “RI-Innovation-Roadmap” published in June 2019, 13 recommendations were listed, as listed in Table 2 below.

Table 3: Summary of the ENVRI services collected

13 RI “Innovation-Readiness” action-plan Recommendations
1. Introduce “Innovation Cooperation with Industry” as a priority in every ENVRI’s Annual Strategic Plan
2. Ensure that its website homepage has a high-level "Industry" or “Innovation” menu tab and section
3. Prepare an annual Innovation and Industry-Liaison Strategy as an annex to the RI Business Plan
4. Hire a full-time Innovation/Industry Liaison officer(s)
5. Hire a Communications Officer(s) with commercial experience
6. Set a target for how much cooperation with Industry should ideally contribute to RI annual revenues (%)
7. Establish a multi-disciplinary, gender-balanced, Industry Advisory Committee
8. Highlight four Industry-cooperation Success Stories on its website and in annual reports to the EC and ESFRI
9. Make sure its Data Portal offers users open, user-friendly access to RI data and services
10. Publish an online RI Services Catalog, inclusive of specific services/opportunities for/with industry
11. On its website, make readily available a standard R Service-level Agreement and IP Policy Guideline for SMEs interested in licensing RI data to (co-)develop value-added products and applications
12. Establish an annual Training Action Plan and Program as annexes to the Business Plan in consultation with industry to bring together RI researchers and company engineers and managers
13. Develop an RI Talent-Attraction Exchange Program with industry to train the next generation of young scientists and engineers

The survey results show that the “innovation-readiness” level is very different depending on ENVRI fields and governance structure. The survey allowed us to revisit those recommendations and assess the status and progress made by ENVRI since 2019. Some RIs have deepened their relationships with the private sector and followed this action list but the innovation readiness is still in progress in most ENVRI.

Further practical recommendations to help RIs develop collaborations with the private sector are listed below.

- FRAMEWORK:**
 The need of having an Innovation or Industry Liaison officer inside each Research Infrastructure was already identified in the frame of ENVRIplus project. It’s well recognized that specialised RI staff could act as facilitators to bridge the gaps between RI and industry. RI industry-liaison staff need to be highly competent, experienced individuals with specific knowledge of technology transfer and commercialization strategies, including patenting processes, along with excellent market insight, extensive professional networks and a clear view and understanding of key science themes and drivers.
 Unfortunately, depending on their structure and targets, some RIs may not have the capacity to hire one person dedicated to innovation. The collaboration with regard to innovation **between several RIs on the same ENVRI domain could be envisaged.**

In the framework of the ENRIITC project⁵, such idea has been further analysed and developed, leading up to propose the creation of an **Industrial Liaison and Contact Officers (ILOs/ICOs)⁶ Hub**

The core activity of the hub would be to provide advice and support to all manner of RIs in their engagement with industry, drawing upon existing experience and good practice and building its body of knowledge as the hub matures. The hub will get a head start by building on the ENRIITC actions and network.

This pan-European “Innovation and industry Services Central Support Hub” (IISCSH) could have the missions to:

- define and update the training path and opportunities for ICOs and ILOs
- offer an exchange platform for collaboration between ILOs/ILOs on innovation
- coordinate the support offer provided to ICOs and ILOs
- coordinate a network level approach with other pan-European entities
- offering a regular source of RI innovation success stories to complement those on RI scientific achievements
- operate an identity for ICOs and ILOs towards other European entities.

Supporting the IISCSH for the part related to ENVRI would be a first step for ENVRI to jointly make progress towards their innovation preparedness.

- **ACTIVITIES:**

Regarding the type of activities most needed to promote an efficient collaboration between Industry sector and Research Infrastructures, increasing the **awareness** is the most critical one.

The ability of the RIs to attract users from the private sector could be linked to the attention put to the dissemination and promotion of the services offered by the RIs. Making information and services offered by RIs understandable to non-traditional end users – not only industry – is crucial.

There is a need for better awareness of the other sector from both sides: it would be valuable for the industry sector to better understand the Research Infrastructures context, while the Research Infrastructures could benefit from knowing the industry segments and the ways they proceed. For example, for industrial stakeholders the landscapes of distributed RIs may be hard to understand.

A set of activities aiming at better promoting the services and added values that RIs can provide as well as actions with the purpose of analysing industry technology needs and their operative constraints should be planned. Such occasions will allow to develop further the trustworthiness feeling from both sides.

Specific actions like participation in trade fairs, developing specific content on the website dedicated to industrial partners and having a clear service definition could be undertaken to increase ENVRI visibility.

- Maintaining a dedicated section of the RIs’ respective main websites and carrying out targeted dissemination campaigns, events and/or specific actions in social media are means to promote ENVRI and their services. Having a dedicated set of “success”

⁵ [ENRIITC](#) is the European Network of Research Infrastructures and Industry for Collaboration. The project main aim is to establish a pan-European network of Industrial Liaison and Contact Officers (ILOs/ICOs) to improve the RI-industry cooperation and boost the innovation ecosystem in Europe.

⁶ According to the [European Commission’s definitions](#) in the [INFRAINNOV-02-2019](#) call text, Industry Liaison Officers (ILO) are officially appointed by the Member States and Associated Countries to stimulate the collaboration among the national industry and the international research infrastructures, providing advice on business opportunities, R&D collaborations, call for tenders and industrial services. Industry Contact Officers (ICO) are research infrastructure staff in charge of developing business relations with all potential industrial suppliers of innovative components or services as well as encouraging the economical use of their facility by private players.

stories would be a way to reply effectively to some requests to participate in industry-related events. These communication and dissemination measures could be further developed with the support of ENVRI-FAIR WP2.

- It has been considered of great value to perform a **market analysis**. This will allow the RIs to better target the industrial segment which are the most relevant for their activities.
- A follow up activity could be envisaged with the industry clients of the RIs that contributed to your survey to ask them if the service catalogue fits their needs. This industrial user feedback survey could include questions about the easiness of access to RIs services, the level of information available about services, issues regarding licences and IPRs.
- Another crucial activity that will enable the strengths of the cooperation between RIs and industry is the **joint development and implementation of project opportunities**, such as E-shape⁷ which enables codesigned pilots with industrial partners.

7 Way forward

Table 4 below indicates the actions which could be taken in the frame of the ENVRI-FAIR project and beyond in order to develop further the work started with this deliverable and efficiently engage ENVRI with industrial stakeholders.

Table 4: List of actions needed to further promote ENVRI's services

Topic	Proposed actions	Reason	Urgency	Responsibility
Uptake of this ENVRI Catalogue of services for private sector users	Further contact the RIs which are currently not included in the services table	Give a better overview of the overall ENVRI community services	short term	WP3 Task 3.4 team
	Implement an online version of the "catalogue" in the ENVRI-Hub and / or ENVRI website	Give better visibility on services available. Easier to update and maintain. Allow to display the information in different ways (filtering)	short term	WP3 Team in collaboration with ENVRI-Hub developer and WP2
	Test the catalogue with ENVRI industrial users to check if it fits their needs	Ensure the relevance of the information displayed, fit to users' need	Short term / medium	WP3
	Promote this "catalogue" in events and on social media once the online version is available	Give better visibility on services available to a large public	Medium	WP3 / WP2
Increase awareness	Update RI website with specific information targeting industry	Increase awareness on what RIs can offer to private sector users	Medium	RI level
	Promote and support the creation / Update of individual RI catalogue of services			RI level

⁷ [e-shape](#) is the flagship European project bringing together key European actors to ensure the optimal implementation of EuroGEO and eventually the delivery of EO-based benefits to a wide range of stakeholders in key societal areas.

	Collect success stories of collaboration between ENVRI and industry	reply effectively to some requests to participate in industry-related events.	Medium /Long term	WP3 / WP2
	Perform a market analysis	Better target industrial segments which are the most relevant for their activities	Medium	RI or subdomain level
Build a sustainable innovation framework	support the creation of an Innovation and industry Services Central Support Hub related to ENVRI	Make progress towards their innovation preparedness	Long term	Beeri, also with the support of external actors (e.g other projects/initiatives)

8 Conclusions

This deliverable reports on the status of the collaboration between ENVRI and industry based on a survey and ENVRI-Fair innovation workshop underlining services relevant for industrial partners. The survey was a way to collect feedback from the different ENVRI in a limited amount of time but some may not have had the opportunity to reply. A first version of a “services for industry catalogue was created. Therefore, we expect this catalogue to evolve in order to add additional services. The current document will be used to promote the existing services inside the ENVRI community and outside, towards the industry. It will enhance the visibility of ENVRI services towards its users and stakeholders. Further work could be undertaken with WP2 “Communications” to better promote the services listed on a sustainable platform (ENVRI-Hub or wiki).

9 Acknowledgements

We gratefully acknowledge the valuable contributions received from the representatives of the Research Infrastructures involved in the BEERI.

Appendix A: Questionnaire

ENVRI services for Industries Catalogue Survey

1. Introduction

Welcome!

This survey is carried out within the framework of the ENVRI-FAIR project (<https://envri.eu/>) funded by the Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 824068.

ENVRI-FAIR (ENVironmental Research Infrastructures building Fair services Accessible for society, Innovation and Research) intends that all participating RIs to have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Task 3.4's objective is to spur innovation by strengthening ENVRI innovation-related cooperation with industry in the development of key RI data service areas- products, technologies and training.

The survey intends to map the services offered by ENVRI and used by private sector users in order to develop a catalogue of RI services targeted for the private sector. This catalogue will improve the visibility of ENVRI to external users. The list of services is not restricted to data services but to all RI services used by private sector users. Your answers will be treated in a strictly confidential manner and will be anonymised for aggregate statistical analysis. *

The personal data collected by the WP3 Task 4 leader in this form (name/email/organisation) will be used only for the deliverable completion. Answers, informed consent and data will be stored at EMSO-ERIC, Italy, for 6 months after the end of the project. Your data will not be used for any other purpose than the establishment of the ENVRI catalogue of services targeted for the private sector and related reporting activities. For more information, please read our privacy notice https://envri.eu/privacy_policy/, and the Google privacy policy <https://policies.google.com/privacy>.

We kindly invite you to share your experience and your views on this topic by participating in this online survey! You will be unable to save your edits but you can download a PDF of the questionnaire so that you may prepare in advance and consult the appropriate personnel where necessary before submitting it online. Only one answer per RI is expected.

For any questions or technical problems, please contact valentina.tegas@emso-eu.org or nalu.franco@plocan.eu. **Deadline for completing the survey is the 18th of February.** Thank you very much for your valuable cooperation!

WP3 Task 3.4 team

**Please note that personal data will be treated confidentially and in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679*

By answering this survey you consent to the collection of your personal data according to the ENVRI-Fair [privacy policy](#).

By clicking yes below, I acknowledge that I have read and understood the information above

- Yes

2. Respondent information:

- 1.1. Name / Surname:
 - 1.2. Organisation:
 - 1.3. RI affiliation:
 - 1.4. Are you a part of a single or distributed RI?
2. If distributed, how many nodes or regional facilities are there?
 - 2.1. Role in the RI:

2.2. E-mail address:

3. Service definition

3.1. What is your field of activity within Earth and environmental sciences?

- Atmosphere
- Ecosystem / Biodiversity
- Marine
- Solid Earth

4. Services offered by your RI:

4.1. Does your RI provide information specifically targeting industry on its website? (*Select one answer*)

- Yes
- No

4.2. Does your RI have a regular (annual, bi-annual, other) Strategy and/or Action Plan for collaboration with companies/industry? (*Select one answer*)

- Yes
- No
- Other, please comment

4.3. Does your Facility have an active Industry Advisory Committee (IAC) or similar industry stakeholder's group? (*Select one answer*)

- Yes
- No

4.4. What kind of services are you offering (or wanting to offer)? (*Multiple choices*)

- Access to facilities / instruments (physical access)
- Access to facilities / instruments (remote access)
- Access to data (virtual access)
- Access to samples
- Analysis service
- Material processing service
- Data management
- Software and applications
- Storage service
- Support service
- Training and education service
- Expertise (consultancy) service, advice
- Infrastructure management service
- Transport service
- Other, please specify: _____

4.5. Which of these services do your industry clients demand the most? (*Please, select up to 5*)

- Access to facilities / instruments (physical access)
- Access to facilities / instruments (remote access)
- Access to data (virtual access)
- Access to samples
- Analysis service
- Material processing service
- Data management
- Software and applications
- Storage service
- Support service

- Training and education service
- Expertise (consultancy) service, advice
- Infrastructure management service
- Transport service
- Other, please specify: _____

4.6. Has your RI developed a service catalogue?

- Yes
- In progress
- No, but we are planning to
- No, we don't

If yes, please provide the link: _____

4.7. Are you offering specific (tailored) services to the private sector?

- Yes
- No

If so, which ones? (*Please describe*)

4.8. Do you have any plan in the future to offer targeted services to the private sector?

4.9. At which stages of the industry's research, development and innovation process did your institution provide support and services? (*Multiple choices*)

- Technology validation
- Technology demonstration
- System demonstration
- Commercialisation

4.10. How did you engage industry for joint research, development and innovation (R&D&I)? (*Multiple choices*)

- Industrial partnership / long-term agreements
- Transfer of technology / licensing
- EU / publicly funded projects
- Industry sponsored / co-financed projects
- Direct company meetings/visits
- Education programmes
- Industry training programmes
- Match-making events

4.11. Which of the following measures do you think help most to strengthen collaboration between your RI and industry? (*Please, select up to 5*)

- Industrial partnership / long-term agreements
- Transfer of technology / licensing
- EU / publicly funded projects
- Industry sponsored / co-financed projects
- Direct company meetings/visits
- Education programmes
- Industry training programmes
- Match-making events

4.12. What size typically are companies using your RI? (*Multiple choices*)

- Start-ups and micro companies (staff headcount: 1-9)
- Small and Medium size companies (SME) (staff headcount: 10-250)

- Large companies (staff headcount: > 250)

4.13. Where are companies using your RI typically located?

- Local (same region as your node/facility)
- From different region in same country as your node/facility
- From other EU country(s)
- International (ex-EU)

Please, specify to which percentage represent each of the categories mentioned above:

4.14. What are the business areas of your RI's actual or potential industrial clients/customers?

4.15. Do you consider collaboration with industry important/useful? (rank from 1 to 5, 1= not important/useful; 5= very important/useful)

4.16. What are the barriers preventing your RI from collaborating with industry/private sector?

- Need for better awareness of the other sector from both sides
- Need for facilitators to bridge the gaps between the two sectors (e.g. Liaison Officer)
- Need for dedicated funded projects (which enable codesigned pilots with industrial partners)
- Need to enhance trustworthiness between the ENVRI and the industry sector
- Other, please comment

5. USAGE of RIs Services/Data on implemented services.

The data collected in this section will be used to feed in the Catalogue of services targeted for the private sector.

5.1. What kind of organization mainly uses your services? (Multiple choices)

- Academia
- Research organization
- Industry
- Public sector

5.2. Can you please complete the following table for each service used by industry? (***The table is available in a separate document. Please, fill as many as needed. You will be asked to upload the document in the google form.***)

LOCATION	Please indicate the location/s of the service provision.
SERVICE NAME	Brief and effective name of the service/resource offered.
TYPE OF SERVICE	Indicate if it is a data service, research service, technical service, innovation service or training service. Multiple choices are possible, though try to be as specific as possible.

SERVICE DESCRIPTION	Short description of what the service/resource does, the functionality it provides and resources it enables to access. Please use max 500 words + link to the RI/Provider website for further info.
TYPE OF ACCESS	Indicate if it is: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● virtual (access to online resource) ● physical (hands-on access with users visiting the facilities in person) ● remote (users do not visit the facility in person)
FREQUENCY OF USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1-2 times per year ● 3-5 times per year ● > 5 times per year ● Other: _____
PRICE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Free of charge ● Charged (depending on user type?)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	Indicate seasonality, if applicable.
CONTACT	Please indicate the name and contacts of the Facility PI.

5.3. Would you like to share success stories on your RI / industry collaboration to be highlighted on the ENVRI community communication channels?

- Yes
- No

6. Policies of your RI affecting the services offered

6.1. Do you have a specific policy for physical access to your services?

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify if there are specific provisions for industry access (e.g. Intellectual Property Rights - IPR)

6.2. Do you have a specific policy for remote access to your services?

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify if there are specific provisions for industry access (e.g. Intellectual Property Rights - IPR)

6.3. Do you have a specific policy for virtual access to your services? If yes, please specify if there are specific provisions for industry access (e.g. IPRs)

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify if there are specific provisions for industry access (e.g. Intellectual Property Rights - IPR)

6.4. Do you have a specific policy/guideline for industry engagement?

- Yes
- No

6.5. Do you have a dedicated person appointed for the relations with industry (Industry liaison officer / Industry Contact Officer or equivalent staff)?

- Yes, part time
- Yes, full time
- No
- Other, please specify _____

Thank you for your time and effort!